

Work Ethics Awareness as Predictors of Administrative Effectiveness of Non-Teaching Staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined work ethics awareness as predictors of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Four research questions guided the study and four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The design for the study was a correlational research design. The population of the study 2,268 non-teaching staff of eight and federal Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The sample size of 340 non-teaching staff (15% of the population) was drawn for the study using simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were researchers-developed questionnaires titled: Work Ethics Awareness Questionnaire (WEAQ) and Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (AEQ). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation by three experts. The reliability of the instruments were determined using Cronbach alpha method which yielded coefficient value of 0.82 for WEAQ and 0.85 for AEQ. Simple regression was used for data analysis. The study showed that work ethics awareness based on age and education is positive and significant predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. It was also found that work ethics awareness based on gender is positive but not a significant predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that management of polytechnics should always organize seminars, workshops and sponsor staff for further learning and training for greater productivity and higher administrative effectiveness as this will go a long way to add value to their work ethics and improved their administrative skills.

Keywords: Work Ethics, Awareness, Administrative Effectiveness, Non-teaching Staff, Polytechnics

Introduction

If all humans have the liberty to live the way the deem fit, without a consideration as to how their self-belief may become an infringement upon the rights of others, this man automatically lead to a total breakdown of law and order. The mere mention of the word ethics, whether in teaching profession, medical profession, political debates or causal conversations among friends or colleagues usually results in a value-laden discussion of what is considered “right” or “wrong”. In schools, non-teaching staff are expected to exhibit acceptance and conventional behaviour that will guarantee quality educational output, promote harmonious relationships and the attainment of

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educational goals. Ethics helps to maintain law and order in schools and it also integrates diverse values that are morally acceptable. Ethics involves doing the right thing always.

The issue of ethics is very important in all organizations be it private or public. This is because every organization is supposed to be guided by certain rules of conduct that treat every member of the organization and stakeholders especially the customers in a dignifying manner. Ethics has to do with how decisions taken by the organizations affect other people and the organizations as well. Ethics is concerned with what is good, and what is desired or preferred human conduct (Uwa *et al.*, 2018). Ethics is concerned with contemporary norms or standard of conduct that govern the relationship among human beings and their institutions. Adinna and Okafor (2023) opined that ethics consists of the fundamental rules or principles according to which behaviours are predicted. For any organization to attain its set goals, the issue of ethics must not be handled with levity. Organization cannot ignore ethics but rather it should be integrated into their daily operations because organization ethics play significant roles in the attainment of organizational objectives, Thus, without work ethics, management and administration of organization could be ineffective.

Effective administration of an organization can no longer be underplayed due to an increase in competition both in product and in service delivery today, that have posed serious challenges for many organizations. Optimal administrative effectiveness of many non-teaching staff is yet to be achieved in many Nigerian polytechnics and this has been one of the major concerns to education stakeholders, if the goals of polytechnic education, according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014), to train technologies, technicians and management skills in courses leading to the award of Certificates, National Diploma (ND), Higher National Diploma (HND) and Advanced Professional Diploma which are relevant to the needs, aspirations and the development of the nation's diverse economy and industries are to be achieved. Polytechnic education is part of technical education programme that leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. It offers knowledge and training geared towards preparing the recipients for special role in the economy. It is with that hope that such acquired training from such Polytechnics would lead to the transformation of the country's economy and industrial development.

Work ethics in education institution include not only how individual workers feel about their jobs, career or vocation, but also, how they do their jobs/responsibilities to meet the predetermined goal of education (Ukala & Nwabueze, 2016). This involves attitude, behaviour, respect, communication, involvement and interaction as well as how one gets along with others in the organization/institution. According to Usman *et al.* (2021), work ethics are accepted standards in terms of personal and social welfare of employee, their work attitude, self-discipline and commitment to their assignments. Work ethics demonstrates many things about whom and how a person is, as well as his functions in organization/institution. It includes individual's characteristics such as honesty, accountability and academic involvement in the education institution. Specifically, work ethics is about what is morally correct, honourable and acceptable to the large majority of the people of an organization, society and group.

Most times, non-teaching staff of Polytechnics seem not to be fully conscious of the ethical implications of their actions, their behaviour is often shaped most significantly by customs and habits (Kathleen *et al.* 2018). It is critical that staff should be aware of the ethical issues in

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institution service delivery and also develop positive perceptions towards them so that they will be in a good position to abide by the code of ethics of the profession. Work ethics awareness is the knowledge and understanding of the acceptable and unacceptable workplace behaviour. It entails the ability of the individual to identify moral and ethical issues and the inclination of the staff to do something about them. It involves all the processes of inculcating moral and ethical values into workers. Personnel can become aware of ethical issues through attendance to conferences and workshops organized by associations or institutions. Awareness on ethical issues will also be enhanced, if institutions, make it mandatory for staff-in-training to offer courses on ethics in service delivery. Khan (2019) stated that factors that determine the work ethics awareness of employees in an organization to include: honesty, integrity, impartiality/fairness, openness, respect for others, reliability and dependability, take initiatives, dedication, accountability, legality, competence, professionalism and humility. In view of this, Eguavoen (2018) opined that personnel must try to realize the work ethics more than ever and comply with the expectation of management to avoid adverse impact on service delivery.

There seems to be unhindered exhibition of unethical behaviour among non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in Nigerian scenario especially in the South East States. These include: ineptitude, indolence, poor interpersonal relationship, negligence, lack of prompt attendance to tasks, absenteeism, unpunctuality, theft, disregard for standards and rules, work rules, harassment and discrimination of students and vulnerable staff, trading in the office during working hours, loitering, soliciting for and receiving of bribe. Others include leaking of examination questions to students, manipulation of examination scores submitted or department for computation and processing, inflation of contracts and supplies, unruly manner of attending to students, lack of respects as human and host of others (Ukala & Nwabueze, 2016; and Nwabueze *et al.*, 2018). This situation is a great deviation from the very high level of ethical standard expected of them.

These acts have devastating implications on the general performance of the institutions. The guess, thus, is that those involved in these acts are bereft of the expected ethical behaviour which is invariably has hampered their compliance and the result is organizational ineffectiveness. Consequent upon this, the general public seems to have lost confidence and trust in the ability of schools, institutions of higher learning and corporations to train individuals to act in an ethical manner. However, with strict adherence to ethical standards, employees would learn to conform, and thereby contribute meaningfully to productivity. Ethical standards are important to ensure that the Polytechnics are operating within the expected and stipulated standards as ethical higher institution of learning. When the administrative practices are done appropriately, it would definitely lead to efficiency, effectiveness and productivity in the school system.

Administrative effectiveness tends to create environment characterized by work ethics (Eguavoen, 2018). Generally, it is perceived that service offered in the Polytechnic settings are based on humanity. The perception is evident in the general assumption that there is generally a poor work ethics in government institutions which largely contribute to low productivity. In line with this, Sharon (2017) observed that employees lacked professionalism and ethics and emphasized the need for staff at different levels to imbibe good work ethics and a sense of professionalism, sine work ethics is associated with productivity. Work ethics help to regulate the activities of employees in different situations in the institution. The habit of following good work ethics is intrinsic, that is, the work ethics an employee displays come from his values. Eguavoen

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(2018) posited that employees' effectiveness at work is determined by their awareness of work ethics and compliance to institutions ethical standards which is largely linked with their demographic variables.

The demographic variables of employees in organizations could be a determining influence on their work ethics awareness, compliance and administrative effectiveness. Thus, employees' demographic variables that are associated with work ethics awareness, compliance and administrative effectiveness in the course of this study include age, gender, education and experience. In support of the above assertion, Bulo et al. (2020) opined that demographic variables of employees in organizations are contributory factors that determine the effectiveness and level of compliance with the code of ethics in any profession. Hence, demographic variables of employees for the course of this study include age, gender, education and experience.

Age plays an important role in effective schools' management. Abiodun (2016) perceived that inactive age as a result of old age affects productivity in Nigerian schools. He also emphasized that the administrators' active achievement age depicts administrative effectiveness with appropriate managerial skills and relationship amongst the staff and subordinates and the host community. Age is the actual number of years a person has lived. It may not be a good determinant of a man's sense of good judgement. Feldman (2017) asserted that the general proposition is that younger administrators in their fifties exhibit better management capabilities than the older administrators since individuals tend to gradually disengage from active work with age. It may as well be that older administrators will be more effective than younger ones, due to vitality and innovativeness associated with being young. The age of an administrator in school determine his/her role for administrative effectiveness. Older administrators are more experienced than newer administrators. Zafer and Aslihan (2016) revealed that older administrators of age 41 years old and above are more effective in handling critical issues as a result of managerial skills than younger administrators in schools. Thus, current findings from Nyagah and Gathumbi (2017) inferred that older administrators were more likely to increase active learning as compared to the middle age and younger administrators in the schools. Since age is a vital component that determines work ethics awareness, compliance and administrative effectiveness, incorporating it in this study could yield a better result in the study area.

Gender is the characteristics that differentiate the masculinity from femininity. It is the societal meaning assigned to male and female. Gender in this study refers to the sex of individual employees either male or female. Gender in effect is determined by the conception of tasks, functions and roles attributed to women and men in society and in public and private life. This is supported by Oboh *et al.* (2020) who reported that gender effect could be a factor in determining the employees' participation in decision-making in Anambra State. Allana et al. (2018) argued that gender is a very relevant and extremely significant in a situation where women are being marginalized. Believes, social norms, behaviour, values, policies, mindsets, processes among others close gross discrimination against women. As administrators' role is very important and crucial in schools in determining performance and achievement, it is very important to look at various roles discriminations existing between the male and the female employees in schools which may influence school effectiveness, Since gender could influence employees' work ethics awareness, compliance and administrative effectiveness which could on the long-run influence organizational performance, considering it in this study will yield positive result.

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Education or educational qualifications can never be over-emphasized. Obadara (2015) described educational qualification as the capacity knowledge that matches or suits an individual making him/her eligible for the office, duty, position, privilege or status. Akande (2017) stated that educational qualification connotes fitness for purpose through fulfillment of necessary conditions such as completion of required schooling and training, or acquisition of a degree, diploma, certificates and professional bodies required through studies. Such educational qualifications include, but are not limited to, the Postgraduate Certificate in Education (PGDE), the Professional Diploma in Education (PDE), Bachelor of Education (B.Ed) and Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) (Abe & Adu, 2013).

Working experience in this study refers to field of knowledge required over months or years of actual practice and which, presumably, has resulted in superior understanding or mastery. That is the process of getting knowledge and skills from doing, seeing, or feeling things. Similarly, experience of an employee is also an influencing factor. Ogbonna and Ebimobowei (2016) stated that experience is the process or fact of personally observing, encountering, or undergoing something. It is possible that educational institutions are handled by experienced non-teaching staff that personally observes the day-to-day code of conducts of their institutions to increase productivity.

Research investigations on the effects of demographic variables such as gender, age, educational level and experience regarding work ethics have been reported in the literature with differing results. As number of studies have reported that females are more likely to exhibit better work attitudes than their male counterparts (Petty & Hill, 2013; and Azam, 2015), while others found no correlation at all between gender and work ethics (Tang, 2016). Petty (2015) found significant differences in work ethics for the age group 36-55 years from the five age groups studies. Some researchers found positive relationships (Wollack, *et al.*, 2011; Goodale, 2013), while others found no relationship (Aldag & Brief, 2014; Buchholz, 2014; MacDonald, 2016) or negative relationships (Tang & Tzeng, 2014) between education and work attitudes. In a recent study, Boatwright and Slate (2017) obtained stronger work ethic values for females; persons aged 20-24 years, and college students than others. It is on the basis of diverse and inconclusive results that this study was conceived to determine the work ethics awareness and administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff in Polytechnics in South East States, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The deteriorating level of administrative effectiveness in Nigeria tertiary institution is fast becoming a serious threat to the survival of institutions in Nigeria which needs to be addressed urgently, and Nigerian Polytechnics are not left out of the scenario. Administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff in Nigerian Polytechnics is a key issue that needs stakeholders' attention. Among the numerous problems confronting Nigerian Polytechnics is the non-performance of some non-teaching staff which is evident in their lack of dedication to work, punctuality, fairness and passion expected of them. The current challenge of the management of Nigerian Polytechnics is to establish an environment that rests on work ethics awareness of the non-teaching staff in the workplace.

Despite all their roles, one of the most serious problems tending to undermine the quality of Polytechnics education in Nigeria (especially in South East States), is the unethical behaviour of non-teaching staff. Over the years, however, there have been some influxes of ethical violations with administrators of the Polytechnics. The unethical behaviours of some administrative staff include diverting some educational facilities provided for institutions development into private use, embezzlement of funds, indiscipline among staff, lateness to work and absenteeism, abuse of power, immorality, financial misconducts, lack of prompt attendance to tasks, unpunctuality, theft, disregard for standards and rules, work rules, harassment and discrimination of students and vulnerable staff, trading in the office during working hours among others.

Furthermore, the managers of the Polytechnics seem also to be faced with the difficulty of assessing the level of work ethics, compliance and administrative effectiveness of the institutions. Inefficiency seems prevalent among the non-teaching staff, most especially, the publicly owned polytechnics in Nigeria (South East States inclusive) when it comes to effective and efficient administrative handling of academic activities with regard to issues concerning students, academic staff, financial planning and budget system/allocation among others. It is in this regard that the study finds it necessary to determine the extent work ethics awareness predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate work ethics awareness and compliance as predictors of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine the extent:

1. work ethics awareness based on age predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
2. work ethics awareness based on gender predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
3. work ethics awareness based on educational level predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
4. work ethics awareness based on experience predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does work ethics awareness based on age predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does work ethics awareness based on gender predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?
3. To what extent does work ethics awareness based on educational level predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

4. To what extent does work ethics awareness based on experience predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Work ethics awareness based on age do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
2. Work ethics awareness based on gender do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
3. Work ethics awareness based on educational level predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.
4. Work ethics awareness based on experience predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The area of the study was South-East States Polytechnics in Nigeria. The choice of the area of the study was informed by the high value placed on education by the government of the South-East States. This high value on education indicates that most of the states in the zone are among the educationally advantaged zones; this is indicated by the federal, state government and privately owned tertiary institutions in the zone. The population of the study comprised 2,268 non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The sample of 340 non-teaching staff (that is, 15% of the population) was used for the study. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used for the study. Stratified sampling technique was used to stratify the non-teaching staff into different stratum where 15% was drawn for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw non-teaching staff from each Polytechnics.

Two sets of questionnaires titled “Work Ethics Awareness Questionnaire (WEAQ)” and “Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (AEQ)” were used for data collection. WEAQ had Sections A and B. Section A was structured to elicit biodata of the respondents, while section which centred on work ethics awareness had 20 items structured on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LW) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. AEQ had Sections A and B. Section A was structured to elicit biodata of the respondents, while section which centred on administrative effectiveness had 20 items structured on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LW) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. The face validation of the instruments were determined by three experts (two in the area of Educational Management and one in the area of

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Measurement and Evaluating) all from the Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Their comments were considered and used in modifying the instruments for final data collection. The reliability of the instruments were established through Cronbach alpha method. The overall reliability coefficients obtained for WEAQ was 0.82 and AEQ was 0.89.

The instruments were administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of six research assistants. Out of the 340 copies of the instruments administered to the respondents, that is 328 (96%) copies of the instruments were correctly filled and returned, while 12(4%) copies of the instruments were either misplaced or not correctly filled. Simple regression was used for data analysis. In answering the research questions, the regression coefficient rule suggested by Stephen (2017) was used for judgement as thus:

Negligible	0.00 - 0.19
Low	0.20 - 0.39
Moderate	0.40 - 0.59
Substantial	0.60 - 0.79
Very High	0.80 - 1.00

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does work ethics awareness based on age predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on age as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β
Constant	36.045	7.539	
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Age	.594	.316	.553
R	.553		
R ²	.488		
Adj. R ²	.427		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that work ethics awareness based on age moderately predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .553$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .488, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 49% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-

teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics awareness based on age of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the claim of the r^2 with a value of .427 indicating that 43% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics awareness based on age). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics awareness based on age is moderately strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .553$) showed that work ethics awareness based on age is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. This is an indication that increase in the age of staff based on the level of awareness lead to .553 (55%) increase in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: To what extent does work ethics awareness based on gender predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on gender as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β
Constant	18.176	3.258	
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Gender	.331	.257	.312
R	.312		
R ²	.228		
Adj. R ²	.205		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that work ethics awareness based on gender lowly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .312$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .228, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was slightly strong. This implies that 23% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics awareness based on gender of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the claim of the r^2 with a value of .205 indicating that 21% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics awareness based on gender). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics awareness based on gender is moderately strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff

of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. However, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .312$) showed that work ethics awareness based on gender is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The positive prediction of staff gender and administrative effectiveness means that the administration of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria does not depend on gender of the staff. Hence, staff gender based on the level of awareness explained .228 (23%) of the variance in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Thus, the implication is that administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria would not depend on whether the staff is a male or female.

Research Question 3: To what extent does work ethics awareness based on educational level predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on educational level as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β
Constant	25.012	5.987	
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Educational Level	.585	.264	.581
R	.581		
R ²	.436		
Adj. R ²	.401		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 indicated that work ethics awareness based on educational level moderately predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .581$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .436, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 44% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics awareness based on educational level of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the claim of the r^2 with a value of .401 indicating that 40% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics awareness based on educational level). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics awareness based on educational level is moderately strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. More so, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .581$) showed that work ethics awareness based on educational level

is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The positive prediction of staff educational level based on work ethics awareness and administrative effectiveness mean that the higher the educational level of staff, the more effective in the administration of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. This further indicated that the more educational qualifications of staff acquire the more effective that he/she becomes in the administration of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Nevertheless, if the staff does not develop academically by acquiring more education, the less effective he/she becomes in the job.

Research Question 4: To what extent does work ethics awareness based on experience predicts administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria?

Table 4: Summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on experience as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β
Constant	35.271	6.815	
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Experience	.592	.349	.588
R	.588		
R ²	.502		
Adj. R ²	.476		

The summary of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 indicated that work ethics awareness based on experience moderately predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria as shown by the regression coefficient ($r = .588$). The coefficient of determination (r^2) .502, showed that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 50% of the variations in administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics, Nigeria were accounted for by the variations in ethics awareness based on experience of the working staff. The adjusted r^2 supported the statement of the r^2 with a value of .476 indicating that 48% of the total variation in the dependent variable (administrative effectiveness) was explained by the independent variable (ethics awareness based on experience). Thus, adjusted r^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of ethics awareness based on experience is moderately strong in determining the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = .588$) showed that work ethics awareness based on experience is a positive predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The positive prediction of staff experience and administrative effectiveness means that the more years in the service, the

more effective the staff in the administration of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. This further indicated that the more the staff serves the more effective he/she becomes in the administration of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: Work ethics awareness based on age do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 5: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on age as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	36.045	7.539		7.149	.000
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Age	.594	.316	.553	11.376	.000
R	.553				
R ²	.488				
Adj. R ²	.437				
F	10.181				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 5 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is .553, while the r^2 is .488 and the adjust r^2 is .427. The F-ratio associated with regression is 10.181, the t-test is 11.376 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on age do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on age significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Work ethics awareness based on gender do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 6: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on gender as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	18.176	3.258		1.094	.000
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Gender	.331	.257	.312	1.681	.000
R	.312				
R ²	.228				
Adj. R ²	.205				
F	3.759				.087

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 6 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is .312, while the r^2 is .228 and the adjust r^2 is .205. The F-ratio associated with regression is 3.759, the t-test is 1.681 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.087) is greater than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on gender do significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on gender do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3: Work ethics awareness based on educational level do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 7: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on educational level as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	25.012	5.987		23.452	.000
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Educational Level	.585	.264	.581	15.271	.000
R	.581				
R ²	.436				
Adj. R ²	.401				
F	26.882				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 7 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is .581, while the r^2 is .436 and the adjust r^2 is .401. The F-ratio associated with regression is 26.882, the t-test is 15.271 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on educational level do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on educational level significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 4: Work ethics awareness based on experience do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria

Table 8: Test of significance of summary of simple regression analysis with work ethics awareness based on experience as predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	35.271	6.815		26.519	.000
Work Ethics Awareness Based on Experience	.591	.349	.588	21.664	.000
R	.588				
R ²	.502				
Adj. R ²	.476				
F	32.427				

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 8 revealed that the simple regression coefficient (r) is .588, while the r^2 is .502 and the adjust r^2 is .476. The F-ratio associated with regression is 32.427, the t-test is 21.664 and the P-value = .000. Since p-value (.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study, therefore, rejected the null hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on experience do not significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work ethics awareness based on experience significantly predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria.

Discussion

Findings on the extent work ethics awareness based on age predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria revealed that work ethics awareness based on age positively and significantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a moderate extent. This result implies there is significance of work ethics awareness based on age predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. The significance of the result is in agreement with the opinion of Akpotu and Leebari (2016) who said that younger employees may prove more vibrant and more academically sound than the older ones, but the younger hand is observed to be queer in the discharge of their administrative functions. It is also in agreement with the opinion of Nwabueze et al (2018) who is of the opinion that individuals' mental, physical and grasp of professional knowledge dwindle with aging. This invariably affects the administrative effectiveness of the administrators. It also in agreement with the opinion of Adekoya et al (2021)

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who said that when an individual grows old, changes that occur in the physical also take place in the central nervous particularly in the relation to the cells of the brain tissue.

Findings on the extent work ethics awareness based on gender predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria indicated that work ethics awareness based on gender positively but insignificantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a low extent. Gender has showed not to be a criterion for staff effectiveness in this study which means that staff effectiveness depends or is based on their capabilities and abilities. The finding of this study is in agreement with that of Bobek et al (2019) whose findings showed that gender has a positive and no significant influence on effectiveness in school management by administrators. The study finding is also in line with the findings of Oboh et al. (2020) who revealed that male employees were not significantly better in supervision than their female counterparts. Thus, the study showed no significant correlation with employees' effectiveness in organizations. This result implies that there is no significant difference in the level of administrative effectiveness between male and female employees in organizations. The insignificant of the result is in agreement with the opinion of Adeyeye et al (2015) who observed that the male principals are not administratively effective than their female counterpart. They attribute this to the fact that men's stamina and ability to work even at stress and other interfering factor can also be withstand more longer than females. The study disagreed with the opinion of Domina (2016) who opined that women performed better when they are heading a single sex school (girl's school) and their performance is observed to be low when they are in-charge of mixed sex school.

Findings on the extent work ethics awareness based on educational level predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria showed that work ethics awareness based on educational level positively and significantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a moderate extent. The educational level of employees from training exposes them to rational thinking for proper analysis of situation before taking decisions. Thus, staff education is a symbol of one's intellectual maturity and experience in decision-making for the best course of action in the work profession. The finding of the study is in consonance with the findings of Adeyemi and Obadiora (2020) that those stakeholders with higher educational qualifications were found to have high level of enforcement of professional ethics compare to those with low educational qualifications. In the words of Usman et al (2021), professionals with higher education qualifications produce quality delivery than those with lower educational qualifications. The similarities of the findings could be as a result of the important of education in the world of work as employees tend to be more confident in their jobs when they have more to offer. The finding of the study has shown that good work ethics awareness helps to improve on administrative

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effectiveness of staff. This is in line with the finding of Sharon (2017) who disclosed that good organizational programmes that promote ethics in an organization were based on the level of education. Employees, who ethically positive, honesty, hardworking and driven by principles of fairness and decency in the workplace, increase the overall morale and enhance the performance of an organization.

Findings on the extent work ethics awareness based on experience predict administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria showed that work ethics awareness based on experience positively and significantly predicted administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria to a moderate extent. This finding has proved that employees do better as they gain experience. Such experience given them extensive repertoires to effectively relate with colleagues, organization and the authorities handling the affairs of the organizations. The finding of the study is in line with the findings of Eguavoen (2018) who revealed that experience was significant factor that moderate the administrative effectiveness to a low a moderate level which have a significant relationship with work ethics. Organizations having more employees with five years and above working experience achieved better results than those having more employees with less than five years working experience. The finding of the study was in line with the findings of Ibrahim and Mohammed (2020) who contended that ethics serves as organizations guide and encourages employees to practice good behaviour for the sake of improving their performance. The similarities observed in the studies could be as a result of importance role of experience in employees' work life which is inevitable.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that work ethics awareness is a positive and significant predictor of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria. Also, work ethics work awareness based on age, gender, educational level and experience are positive and significant predictors of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East, Nigeria except gender which is not significant. The study showed that ethics serves as organizations' guide and encourage employees to practices good behaviour for the sake of improving their performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of polytechnics should always organize seminars, workshops and sponsor staff for further learning and training for greater productivity and higher administrative effectiveness as this will go a long way to add value to their work ethics and improved their administrative skills.

2. The management of polytechnic should ensure proper application of work ethics in the school system to create peaceful environment that could promote and increase the strength of achieving educational set goals and objectives with a given period.
3. Work ethics based on age, education level and working experience of staff should be in consideration during promotion and recruitment of staff because these variables had shown to be positive and significant predictors of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff of Polytechnics in South East.

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